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Quercetin and COVID-19

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

Quercetin supplementation together with multivitamin and trace elements supplementation (especially vitamins C and D, zinc) can be useful in prophylaxis and treatment of mild symptomatic COVID-19 patients, but more clinical research is mandatory to determine the exact clinical efficacy and dose regimen.

QUERCETIN AND SARS-CoV-2

Quercetin, a naturally occurring dietary flavonoid, is well known to ameliorate chronic diseases and aging processes in humans, and its antiviral properties have been investigated in numerous studies. In silico and in vitro studies demonstrated that quercetin can interfere with various stages of the coronavirus entry and replication cycle such as PLpro, 3CLpro, and NTPase/helicase. Due to its pleiotropic activities and lack of systemic toxicity, quercetin and its derivatives may represent target compounds to be tested in future clinical trials to enrich the drug arsenal against coronavirus infections. There is evidence that quercetin in combination with, for example, vitamins C and D, may

exert a synergistic antiviral action that may provide either an alternative or additional therapeutic/preventive option due to overlapping antiviral and immunomodulatory properties¹.

In a case series study (Kamel and coworkers, 2020) done on twenty-two COVID-19 patients confirmed to be infected with SARS-CoV-2, researchers prescribed quercetin 800 mg, bromelain 165 mg, zinc acetate 50 mg and ascorbic acid 1 g once daily as supplements for 3 to 5 days during SARS-CoV-2 infection. In addition to quercetin and bromelain supplements, most of the twenty-two patients enrolled in the study were on hospital medications which include vitamin C, zinc, enoxaparin, drugs expected to have an anti-SARS-CoV-2 effect (ribavirin, hydroxychloroquine or lopinavir-ritonavir) and antibacterial drugs. All the patients' laboratory tests done at admission and at discharge were not significantly different. The mean days of stay at the hospital were 9 days. These results reveal that quercetin 800 mg once daily with bromelain 165 mg, in addition to zinc acetate 50 mg and vitamin c 1 g supplements are safe with COVID-19

patients who were on multiple therapies including antivirals and antibacterial medications. The efficacy of quercetin, bromelain, zinc and ascorbic acid combination was not clear in this study, because of lacking placebo or comparable group; however, their efficacy in preventing severe consequences of SARS-CoV-2 infections cannot be ruled out based on previous studies².

There is evidence that vitamin C and quercetin co-administration exerts a synergistic antiviral action due to overlapping antiviral and immunomodulatory properties and the capacity of ascorbate to recycle quercetin, increasing its efficacy³.

As quercetin is reported to be effective on treatment and prophylaxis of other SARS like coronavirus infections, as a strong antioxidant and scavenger flavonoid without any adverse events, the investigators of the ongoing clinical trial (NCT04377789) hypothesize that quercetin can be effective on both prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19 cases⁴.

Paul Marik, MD, Chief of Pulmonary and Critical Care Medicine, Eastern Virginia Medical School, Norfolk, VA developed a COVID-19 protocol that includes Quercetin 250 mg daily for COVID-19 prophylaxis and 250-500 mg BID for

mildly symptomatic patients⁵, but there are no available published follow-up data to confirm the efficacy of this protocol.

CONCLUSION

Quercetin is a naturally occurring dietary flavonoid. In silico and in vitro studies demonstrated that quercetin can interfere with various stages of the coronavirus entry and replication cycle such as PLpro, 3CLpro, and NTPase/helicase. There is evidence that quercetin in combination with vitamins C and D may exert a synergistic antiviral action. Quercetin supplementation is found to be safe with COVID-19 patients who were on multiple therapies including antivirals and antibacterial medications. Therefore, quercetin supplementation together with multivitamin and trace elements supplementation (vitamins A, B complex, C, D and E, zinc) can be useful in prophylaxis and treatment of mild symptomatic COVID-19 patients.

Of course, more clinical research is mandatory to determine the exact clinical efficacy and dose regimen for quercetin, before creating any official guidelines for COVID-19 prophylaxis and treatment.

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